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Nomenclature

Abbreviations

BECCS	Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage	-
CC	Combined Cycle	-
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage	-
CLC	Chemical Looping Combustion	-
GT	Gas Turbine	-
HRSG	Heat Recovery Steam Generator	-
NGCC	Natural Gas Combined Cycle	-
PCLC	Pressurized Chemical Looping Combustion	-

Symbols

b_r	Stoichiometric factor in the reduction reaction	-
c_g	Specific heat capacity of particles	J/kgK
c_p	Specific heat capacity of gas	J/kgK
E	Activation Energy for the chemical reaction	kJ mol^{-1}
F_f	Molar flow of the fuel gas	mol/s
g	Acceleration due to gravity, 9.81	m s^{-2}
G_s	Solid circulation rate	$\text{kg}/(\text{m}^2 \text{ s})$
H_0	Enthalpy of formation	kJ mol^{-1}
M	Molecular Mass	g

m_{ox}	Mass of the oxygen carrier which has been oxidised	Kg
m_{ox_FR}	Solids inventory of the fuel reactor	Kg
m_{ox_AR}	Solids inventory of the air reactor	Kg
m_{red}	Mass of the oxygen carrier which has been reduced	kg
\dot{m}_{ox}	Circulation rate of the oxygen carrier, expressed as the mass of oxygen carrier totally oxidised	Kg/s
\dot{m}	Real circulation rate	Kg/s
P	Operating pressure	MPa
\bar{r}	Solid reaction rate of the reaction	mol of solid (m ³ of solid) ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
R_0	Oxygen Transport Capacity	-
x_{NiO}	Mass fraction of NiO in the fully oxidized sample	-
$X_{S,o}$	Solids conversion in the oxidation reaction	-

Greek letters

α	Equivalence ratio	-
ΔX_f	Variation in the Conversion rate of fuel	-
ΔX_g	Variation in the Conversion rate of gas	-
ΔX_s	Variation in the Conversion rate of solid	-
ρ_g	Gas density	kg/m ³
ρ_p	Solids (particle) density	kg/m ³
τ	Time for the complete conversion of the solid, for reduction or oxidation reaction	s
Φ	Characteristic reactivity in the air reactor	-

SECTION 1: INTRODUCTION

The project GTCLC-NEG foresaw a secondment with Baker Hughes Company production site in Florence. The foreseen activities were:

- a model of the CLC combustor with biofuels will be integrated with the NOVA LT16 gas turbine in BHGE (during the secondment).
- a technical analysis using BHGE proprietary models, to optimize turbine working conditions using hot air instead of exhaust combustion gases.

This work ended up with guidelines to design and optimize a combustor for gas turbines based on CLC technology.

Main results are proposed in the next paragraphs.

SECTION 2: METHODOLOGY

Gas Turbine data sheet

The NOVALT16 gas turbine is characterized by high efficiency and minimal overall cost. The combustion system can reduce emissions of NO_x to 15 ppm. The engine design uses adjustable nozzle guide vanes to achieve high efficiency at partial load.

Figure 1: NOVALT16 gas turbine

The generator has a drive power of 16.9 MW and a mechanical drive power of 17.5 MW. Most important technical specifications are shown in table 1¹.

¹ <https://www.kts-eng.com/en/product/nova-lt16-gas-turbines/>

Table 1: NOVALT16 gas turbine technical specifications

NovalT 16	Unit of measurement	Generator drive	Mechanical drive
Power	MW	16.9	17.5
Efficiency	%	36.4	37.4
NOx	ppm	15	15
Exhaust gas temperature	°C	495	495
Speed	rpm	7 800	7 800
Length-Width-Height	m	15.62 x 3.15 x 9.52	12.5 x 3.15 x 4.1
Weight	tonnes	134	52.9
Service intervals			
Hot runner inspection (medium repairs)	hours	35 000	35 000
Major repairs	hours	70 000	70 000

Combustor design guidelines

The guidelines to design the Gas Turbine combustor have been developed together with Baker Hughes company and published on [1] and further improved with the ASPEN Model realized and described in deliverable D3.3 and published in [2] and [3].

In this section we describe the final results of the guidelines which are reported in figure 2. This describes the practical steps (or guidelines) to be followed in the design of the plant. In the next section it is shown also an example of the application of the guidelines, assuming that the plant is fed with syngas produced from biomass gasification (as an example).

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Figure 2: Procedure for the design of the PCLC-based carbon negative emissions power plant [2, 3] elaborated from [4] and [5]

We see from Figure 2 that for the design of the pressurized Chemical Looping Plant to be coupled to a gas turbine the following steps have to be undertaken: be coupled to a gas turbine the following steps have to be undertaken:

1. Firstly the power capacity of the gas turbine is considered and based on this the air mass flow is calculated, using Aspen Plus and assuming an excess air value which is iteratively optimized trying to reduce fuel consumption and maintaining a Turbine Inlet Temperature constant at 1200°C;
2. Then from the stoichiometric air flow the fuel consumption is calculated (and it is used iteratively to optimize excess air consumption);
3. From the optimization process the air reactor and fuel reactor specification are determined, which are used to calculate the mass and energy balances of the air reactor and fuel reactor;
4. Then from the box delimited with red dotted lines which is about mass and energy balances optimization we pass to the box delimited with blue dotted lines which is instead on the hydrodynamics optimization we want in fact that both the air reactor and the fuel reactor are close to the fast fluidization regime which allows us to reduce the inventory and so also the

operating costs of the plant. This is done by drawing the Grace diagram as it will be shown later.

SECTION 3: CASE STUDY

Choosing the plant layout

The procedure presented in figure 2 sees as a first step, the identification of a certain plant layout. In this particular case the layout has been already identified and it is reported in the GTCLC-NEG project documents themselves as they were submitted to the European Commission. Here we propose a slightly modified diagram.

Figure 3: GTCLC-NEG plant layout [2]

It is obviously based on the state of the art presented in [1] and it is a configuration in which both: the depleted air coming from the air reactor expands in a turbo expander. The expanded gases (which have produced electrical power) are used then to recover heat in two HRSGs. The exhaust gases exiting the fuel reactor are used for thermal recovery maintaining them at pressurized conditions to spare the energy which will be needed in a second time to liquefy the CO₂.

Setting the power capacity of the turbine, the air mass flow and the fuel mass flow

If we assume a power of 12 MWe of the turbo expander, we can then model the plant in ASPEN Plus v11 (see figure 4) and calculate in detail:

- the air mass flow (which in this case it is equal to 135 t/h);
- the diameter and the length of the fluidized bed reactor, which is used as an air reactor and so it is configured as a riser.

The power capacity of 12 MWe is chosen because, working with biofuels the scale of the plant is limited by biomass availability and also because of the set of products offered on the market by main gas turbines producing companies.

Figure 4: Aspen Plus project of the air reactor (AR) and fuel reactor (FR)

Calculating the oxygen carrier circulation rate and the solids inventory

The circulation rate is calculated mainly based on a mass balance applied to the fuel reactor and depends on the conversion variation of the oxygen carrier, obtained in the fuel and air reactor.

Given that the flow of syngas is already known, we can calculate the circulation rate, according to equations 1 and 2, taken from [6].

$$\dot{m}_{\text{ox}} = b_r M_{\text{NiO}} F_f \Delta X_f / (X_{\text{NiO}} \Delta X_s) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{m} = \dot{m}_{\text{ox}} (1 + R_0 X_{\text{NiO}} (X_{S,0} - 1)) \quad (2)$$

Where equation (1) represents the recirculation rate, expressed as the mass of oxygen carrier totally oxidized, while equation (10) is the real recirculation rate. The parameters shown in equations (9) and (10) are explained in the following paragraphs:

- b_r is the stoichiometric factor in the reduction reactions, expressed in mol of solid reacting per mol of fuel gas. In particular if we refer to the fuel reactor, we will have to consider the following reactions:

In reality, if we use oxygen carriers based on nickel oxides, we have also to consider the water-gas-shift reaction.

- M is the molecular weight of the material, expressed in g per mole;
- F_f is the molar flow of the fuel gas, expressed in moles/s;
- ΔX_f is the conversion rate of the fuel gas, which is assumed to be equal to 1;

- x_{NiO} is the mass fraction of NiO in the fully oxidized sample; this parameter can be inferred directly from name of the oxygen carrier, for example if we take into consideration Ni₄₀Al-FG: the two last letters mean freeze granulation, while the number 40 means 40% in mass of nickel metal is contained. This oxygen carrier has been tested in pressurized conditions at the Instituto de Carboquímica, see [7];
- ΔX_s represents the variation in the solids conversion. In fact not all the solids which are circulating in the reactor are fully converted, we can assume that 30% of the solids is converted, as reported for example in: [6].
- another key parameter of the oxygen carrier, after the mass fraction of metal, is the R_0 , which is the oxygen transport capacity of the active metal oxide (for active metal oxide we indicate the part of the metal oxide which has not reacted with the support and so can actively behave as an oxygen carrier). These two data: mass fraction of metal oxide and oxygen transport capacity are indicated in Table 2 for Ni₄₀Al-FG and are key parameters also for the design of the fuel and air reactor. R_0 can be calculated according to equation 5, as reported in [8];

$$R_0 = (m_{\text{ox}} - m_{\text{red}})/m_{\text{ox}} \quad (5)$$

where m_{ox} and m_{red} are the masses of the oxidized and reduced form of the oxygen carrier, respectively.

- $X_{S,o}$ is the solids conversion in the oxidation reaction and can be calculated from equation 6.

$$X_{S,o} = 1 - \frac{m_{\text{ox}} - m}{m_{\text{ox}} R_0 X_{\text{NiO}}} \quad (6)$$

Where m is the mass of the sample. In reality in this case we assume that:

- in the air reactor the oxygen carrier enters with $X_o = 0.5$ and exits with $X_o = 0.8$;
- in the fuel reactor the oxygen carrier enters with $X_r = 0.2$ and exits with $X_r = 0.5$
- the variation in solids conversion rate for reduction (ΔX_r) and the variation in solids conversion rate for oxidation (ΔX_o) are both equal to 0.3.

The main characteristics of the oxygen carrier used are shown in table 2.

As said before the oxygen carrier is derived from a freeze granulation preparation process, performed at Chalmers University, according to what

reported in [9]. Based on equations 1 and 2 the final calculation of the circulation rate results to be equal to 111 kg/s, which is not excessive for a power plant producing 12 MWe and considering also other values reported in literature, see [6].

Table 2. Ni40Al-FG Oxygen carrier characteristics [7]

<u>Parameter</u>	Value	Unit of measure
Active NiO content	40	wt%
Oxygen transport capacity	0.084	-
Particle size	0.2	(μm)
Porosity	0.36	%
Specific surface area (BET)	0.8	m^2/g
Solid density	5380	kg/m^3

Also in the case of the solids inventory, this important design parameter is obtained from a mass balance performed at the air reactor and at the fuel reactor. So in this case we will have an optimal inventory for the air reactor and an optimal inventory of the fuel reactor. As already said these inventories will influence the bed height and the pressure drop so in the end also the pressure drop has to be checked to know if the two inventories are reasonable.

Based on a mass balance for both air reactor and fuel reactor the mass of oxygen carrier which is totally oxidized can be calculated based on the molar flow of the fuel gas [6]:

$$m_{ox,FR} = \frac{\rho_{NiO} b_r F_f}{x_{NiO} (-\bar{r}_{NiO})_r} \quad (7)$$

$$m_{ox,AR} = \frac{M_{NiO}}{M_{Ni}} \frac{\rho_{NiO} b_r F_f}{x_{NiO} (-\bar{r}_{Ni})_o} \quad (8)$$

Where:

- $m_{ox,FR}$ and $m_{ox,AR}$ are the inventory in the fuel reactor and in the air reactor, respectively.
- ρ_{NiO} is the density of the oxygen carrier, as reported in table 2;

- $(-\bar{r}_{NiO})_r$ and $(-\bar{r}_{Ni})_o$ are the average reactions rate of the oxygen carrier per unit volume of the reacting solid, which can be calculated as explained in [6].

Equations 8 and 7 can be re-written in a simpler way, as also equation 9.

$$\mathbf{m}_{OC} = \mathbf{y}_g \Delta \mathbf{X}_g \frac{2dM_o}{R_o} \frac{\bar{\tau}_r}{\Phi_{FR}} \quad (9)$$

Equation 9 is for the determination of the solids inventory of the fuel reactor. For the determination of the inventory of the oxygen carrier in the air reactor we simply substitute the $\bar{\tau}_r$ and the Φ_{FR} with $\bar{\tau}_o$ and Φ_{AR} . Dealing with the other parameters, y_g can be considered equal to 1, $\Delta \mathbf{X}_g$ is equal to 0.999. While R_o is a parameter which is typical of the oxygen carrier, d is typical of the reaction. In fact, d is the stoichiometric factor in the fuel combustion reaction with oxygen (expressed in mol O_2 per mol of fuel). M_o is the molar mass of oxygen (so it is 16). The expression: $\frac{2dM_o}{R_o}$ represents the characteristic circulation rate (also the enthalpy of reaction can be included in the expression at the denominator if we want to express

the characteristic circulation rate based on the MW of primary energy of the reactor), also identified with the symbol: \dot{m}_c .

The parameter Φ_{FR} is the characteristic reactivity, which depends by the solid conversion at the inlet, $X_{r,in}$, and the variation of solids conversion ΔX_r , see [10].

The final inventory of the whole plant is given, obviously, by the sum of the inventory of the fuel reactor and that of the air reactor. If we have a fuel, like syngas, composed by two burning species (like H_2 and CO) the inventory of the fuel reactor will be the sum of the inventories which are necessary to oxidise hydrogen and carbon monoxide.

Designing the air reactor and the fuel reactor

Based on the plant realized in Aspen Plus v11, the design of the air reactor is performed, and we obtained a reactor with circular section and height of 9.5 meters and diameter of 2 meters due to the important amount of air which needs to flow through it (135 t/h). The air reactor is operated in a fast fluidization regime with a very small height of the bed bottom zone, while the height of the freeboard is important. Given the high mass flow the velocity is also high and this increases the elutriation index and the transport disengaging height. The pressure drop is about 0.5 bar. This

value is also confirmed by some literature published on the topic, see [11]. This means that the influence of the pressure drop on the final plant efficiency is quite limited, while much more important is the influence of the inlet temperature of the air expanding in the turbo expander. This is assumed to be about 1300°C at a pressure equal to 12 bar.

Calculating and optimized plant efficiency

The temperature of 1300°C, at the exit of the air reactor, is based on the consideration that the enthalpy of reaction inside the air reactor is sufficient to heat up the incoming air and the circulating oxygen carrier. We have to consider in fact that the air, once it is compressed at 12 bar has already increased its enthalpy to 0.688 MJ/kg (as calculated by Aspen Plus V11). Knowing the enthalpy of the compressed air, we need to know then the enthalpy of the oxidation reaction, this data has been tabulated in [12] and are proposed in table 3.

It is important noting from table 3 that negative numbers of ΔH_r^0 indicate exothermic reactions, while positive numbers of ΔH_r^0 indicate endothermic reactions.

Table 3: Standard heat of reactions (ΔH_r^0) for the reduction and oxidation reactions of different oxygen carriers. Where the data are referred to 1 mole of gas or carbon and the units of measure are kJ/mol [12]

Redox system	ΔH_r^0 (kJ/mol gas or C)				
	CH ₄	H ₂	CO	C	O ₂
CaSO ₄ /CaS	158.6	-1.6	-42.7	86.9	-480.5
Co ₃ O ₄ /Co	107.9	-14.3	-55.4	61.6	-455.1
Co ₃ O ₄ /CoO	-16.8	-45.5	-86.6	-0.8	-392.7
CoO/Co	149.5	-3.9	-45.0	82.4	-475.9
CuO/Cu	-178.0	-85.8	-126.9	-81.4	-312.1
CuO/Cu ₂ O	-236.6	-100.4	-141.6	-110.7	-282.8
Cu ₂ O/Cu	-119.5	-71.1	-112.3	-52.1	-341.4
CuAl ₂ O ₄ /CuAl ₂ O ₃	282.2	29.3	-11.8	148.7	-542.2
CuAlO ₂ /CuAl ₂ O ₃	-24.1	-47.3	-88.4	-4.4	-389.1
CuAl ₂ O ₄ /CuAlO ₂	588.5	105.9	64.7	301.9	-695.4
Fe ₂ O ₃ /Fe ₃ O ₄	141.6	-5.8	-47.0	78.4	-472.0
Fe ₂ O ₃ /FeO	318.4	38.3	-2.8	166.8	-560.3
Fe ₂ O ₃ Al ₂ O ₃ /FeAl ₂ O ₄	-62.3	-56.8	-98.0	-23.5	-370.0
Fe ₂ TiO ₅ /FeTiO ₃	106.5	-14.6	-55.8	60.9	-454.4
Mn ₂ O ₃ /MnO	-48.0	-53.3	-94.4	-16.4	-377.1
Mn ₂ O ₃ /Mn ₃ O ₄	-396.6	-140.4	-181.6	-190.7	-202.8
Mn ₃ O ₄ /MnO	126.3	-9.7	-50.8	70.8	-464.3
NiO/Ni	156.5	-2.1	-43.3	85.9	-479.4
NiAl ₂ O ₄ /NiAl ₂ O ₃	158.6	-1.6	-42.8	86.9	-480.4

Taking into account the data shown in the table 9 and the data on the enthalpy of the compressed air fed to the air reactor (AR), the AR energy balance can be calculated with the following equation:

$$Q_{AR} = [H_{MeO}^0 * m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{AR} - T_0)] - [(H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{AR} - T_{FR})) + ((m_{O2st} * (alfa) * cp_{O2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})) + (m_{N2st} * alfa * cp_{N2} * (T_{AR} - T_{comp})))] + VR * \Delta P \quad (10)$$

Where:

- Q_{AR} is the heat generated in the air reactor and then exchanged with the fuel reactor;
- H_{Me}^0 is the enthalpy of formation of the metal in its reduced form; H_{MeO}^0 is relative to the oxidized form;
- m_{Me} is the mass of the reduced metal; m_{MeO} is relative to the oxidized form;
- cp_{Me} is the specific heat of the reduced metal; cp_{MeO} is relative to the oxidized form;
- T_{AR} is the temperature of the air reactor, which is set to be 1300°C because it coincides with the turbine inlet temperature (TIT);
- T_0 is the standard temperature;
- T_{FR} is the temperature of the fuel reactor, which is set to be about 50°C less than that of the Air Reactor, see [10];

- $m_{O_{2st}}$ is the mass of oxygen which reacts with the oxygen carrier oxidizing it;
- α is the ratio between the actual oxygen and the stoichiometric oxygen which reacts with the oxygen carrier; it represents the unknown in the equation;
- $c_{p_{O_2}}$ is the specific heat of the oxygen;
- T_{comp} is the temperature at the exit of the compressor;
- $m_{N_{2st}}$ is the mass of the nitrogen contained in stoichiometric air;
- $c_{p_{N_2}}$ is the specific heat of nitrogen;
- V_R is the volume of the reactor;
- ΔP is the pressure loss , due to the bed height and the injection system as well.

Equation 10 has two unknowns: the heat which is provided at the fuel reactor by the oxygen carrier which circulates and so not only transports its mass from one reactor to another, but also transports energy in form of heat. The term indicated as Q_{AR} is the heat of the air reactor, which at equilibrium is equal to the heat adsorbed by the fuel reactor (if we assume

that the losses are zero). For this reason, the excess air results to be the only unknown in a system of two equations. In this way iteratively we are able to determine what is the fuel mass flow, based on the optimal excess of air. Where the optimal excess of air is defined as the one which can still provide a temperature of the exiting gases which is set at about 1300°C. Equation 11 is based on the difference between the enthalpy of the products and the enthalpy of the reagents of the reactions happening in the Fuel Reactor.

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_{FR} = & [(H_{CO_2}^0 * m_{CO_2} + m_{CO_2} * cp_{CO_2} * (T_{FR} - T_0)) + (H_{H_2O}^0 * m_{H_2O} + \\
 & m_{H_2O} * H_{H_2O}) + (H_{Me}^0 * m_{Me} + m_{Me} * cp_{Me} * (T_{FR} - T_0))] - [(H_{MeO}^0 * \\
 & m_{MeO} + m_{MeO} * cp_{MeO} * (T_{FR} - T_{AR})) + (H_{CO}^0 * m_{CO} + m_{CO} * cp_{CO} * \\
 & (T_{FR} - T_{comp}) + (H_{H_2}^0 * m_{H_2} + m_{H_2} * cp_{H_2} * (T_{FR} - T_{comp}))] + VR * \Delta P
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

Where:

- Q_{FR} is the heat absorbed by the Fuel Reactor;

- $H_{CO_2}^0$ is the enthalpy of formation of CO_2 ;

- m_{CO_2} is the mass of CO_2 ;
- cp_{CO_2} is the specific heat of CO_2 ;
- $H^0_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the heat of formation of H_2O ;
- $m_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the mass of water;
- $H_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ is the enthalpy of water, which takes into account: heating evaporation and further heating at the Fuel Reactor temperature;
- H^0_{CO} and $H^0_{\text{H}_2}$ are respectively the enthalpies of formation of carbon monoxide and hydrogen;
- m_{CO} and m_{H_2} are respectively the masses of carbon monoxide and hydrogen;
- cp_{CO} and cp_{H_2} are respectively the specific heats of carbon monoxide and hydrogen.

SECTION 4: CONCLUSIONS

This work, developed under the framework of the Marie Curie Project GTCLC-NEG, gives some guidelines and theoretical principles on the design of a Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage plant based on the coupling of Chemical Looping Combustion with a turbo expander. A

careful literature review has been made on the possible efficiencies, which can be gained with such a plant that represents a technological alternative to Natural Gas Combined Cycles with CCS. Usually this last type of plants can reach very high electrical efficiencies, but when they are coupled with carbon capture and storage they undergo an energy penalty, which can be comprised between 8-10%.

Finally after the state of the art on pressurized chemical looping combustion the paper presents some guidelines for designing pressurized fluidized bed combustors to be coupled with turbo expanders in carbon negative emissions power plants:

- the first step is to select the capacity of the desired turbine, based also on the biomass available in the territory where the project is developed;
- the second is to take into consideration the desired specifications of the turbine (like the turbine inlet temperature and the compression ratio);
- the third is to identify the mass flow of air;
- the fourth is to use a balance of energy applied to the fuel and air reactor to optimize the quantity of excess air reducing the use of fuel and granting high temperatures at the inlet of the turbine,
- the fifth is to identify in a recursive way the optimal quantity of fuel;

- the sixth is to calculate the oxygen carrier circulation rate;
- the seventh is to calculate the oxygen carrier inventory;
- the eighth is to calculate detailed mass and energy balances of the plant and so its efficiency.

Further steps will take into account the economic feasibility and optimization of such plants.

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